

Study of Eosinophilia in Blood Donors in a Tertiary Care Centre in South India

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Abstract

Eosinophil is a type of granulocyte in blood. They are activated by IL-3, IL-5 and GM-CSF. Eosinophilia means increase in number of eosinophils in blood. Even with raised level of eosinophils, subjects show no signs or symptoms associated with any known etiology of eosinophilia. In this present study aim to observe eosinophilia in voluntary blood donors. The present hospital based cross sectional study was conducted in blood bank of Trichy SRM Medical College Hospital and Research Institute over a period of 12 months. Around 1258 blood donors was selected based on the convenient sampling method. Blood is obtained from the veins of the antecubital fossa and complete blood cell count was done using complete blood count analyzer. The mean age of the study participant was 25.72 ± 7.52 years. Majority of the study participant was males which is 1240 (99.2%) participants. The median total count was 7.22 (IQR – 2.89) mm³ and the median eosinophil count was 0.25 (IQR – 0.23) cells/mcL. Out of 1258 blood donors, 142 (11.3%) had mild eosinophilia and 6 (0.5%) had moderate eosinophilia. The median total count was significantly higher among moderate eosinophilia blood donors when compared to mild eosinophilia and normal blood donors. Eosinophilia, a common abnormal condition found during routine physical examinations is often misdiagnosed by general practitioners. In endemic areas empirical anthelmintic treatment has been effective for managing eosinophilia. Further research is needed for chronic eosinophilia, especially in those with malignancy.

Keywords: Blood Donors – Eosinophilia

Introduction

Eosinophilia is a disorder characterized by an eosinophil count in the peripheral blood that above the normal range; the most widely accepted criteria is an absolute eosinophil count (AEC) over 500 cells/ μ L (1-5). Eosinophilia can be categorized based on severity: mild (AEC 501–1499 cells/ μ L), moderate (AEC 1500–4999 cells/ μ L), and severe (AEC \geq 5000 cells/ μ L) (6,7). Eosinophilia is a prevalent disorder frequently identified by automated complete blood count (CBC) results, with prevalence rates varying from 0.1% to 77.5% depends on the research context and demographic (8-10).

Eosinophilia's underlying causes may be roughly categorised into three groups as follows. The most common cause of eosinophilia is secondary/reactive eosinophilia, which is caused by cytokine-driven reactive phenomena from various primary conditions, including atopy and parasite infection (2); clonal eosinophilia, which is caused by mutations that result in the clonal expansion of eosinophils, such as in haematological neoplasms; and (3) idiopathic eosinophilia, for which the cause remains unknown even after extensive research (11,12).

Eosinophilia may emerge often in the clinical practice consequently and been connected with many causes and cohorts: (i) Allergy-related immunological conditions (such as asthma, eosinophilic oesophagitis, and other conditions, etc.) (ii) medication reactions (e.g., drug reaction with eosinophilia and systemic symptoms—DRESS-), (iii) rheumatologic/connective tissue diseases (e.g., eosinophilic granulomatosis with polyangiitis, etc.), (iv) cancers (mostly linked to haematological neoplasm, etc.), (v) parasitic and other infections (significant in migrants and travellers from developing nations), (vi) insufficiency of the adrenal gland, and (vii) other (13-20).

Over the past two decades, researchers have made significant progress in understanding the mechanisms of eosinophil production, programmed cell death, and eosinophil immunology. The primary stimuli for eosinophil production are interleukin (IL)-5, IL-3, and granulocyte-macrophage colony-stimulating factor (GM-CSF), which also inhibit eosinophil programmed cell death. Eosinophilia can be triggered by increased eosinophil production, longevity, or a combination of these (21,22).

Eosinophils migrate from their bone marrow production site into the blood and peripheral tissues, producing various cytokines and cationic proteins. These include IL-2, IL-3, IL-4, IL-5, IL-7, IL-13, IL-16, TNF-alpha, TGF-beta, and RANTES. Eosinophils also contribute to immunologic responses against infectious disease agents and tissue damage in allergic and autoimmune diseases (23,24). HES, or idiopathic hypereosinophilic syndrome, is

an uncommon illness. The World Health Organisation projects an incidence rate that is age-adjusted to be around 0.036 per 100,000 people (25).

Blood donation centers are entrance doors to healthcare facilities and can be considered a place for medical research. Though routine screening measure gets undertaken in blood donation, eosinophilia in blood donors was documented in different studies. The rationale for studying blood donors involved with eosinophilia is because it could bridge a few gaps regarding the studies already available. There have been various studies about eosinophilia in clinical settings, and yet such information is scarce in a group of blood donors.

Donors are generally a representation of the cross-section of a population, consisting of donors from all age groups, socio-economic backdrops and geographic locations. Understanding the causes of eosinophilia in a blood donor may have relevance for donor screening and management. General causes might be addressed by health care professionals when evaluating a potential donor for eligibility and appropriate follow-up care. This study's objective was to evaluate eosinophilia in a group of blood donors who were recruited during a 12 month period.

Materials and Methods

This is a hospital based cross sectional study was conducted in blood bank of Trichy SRM Medical College Hospital and Research Centre. The study was conducted over a period of 12 months. All eligible voluntary blood donors who fit for blood donation were the study participants. Convenient sampling method is used and around 1258 blood donors was selected based on the following inclusion and exclusion criteria. This study was approved by Institutional Ethics Committee (Ref: 433/ TSRMMCH&RC/ ME-1/ 2023 – IEC No. 015 dated 05.04.2023).

All eligible voluntary blood donors 18-60 years of age who is willing to give consent for the study was included. Pregnant and menstruating women, those who take medication such as ACE inhibitors, anticonvulsant, antimalarials, antiretroviral, antidiabetic drugs, antibiotics and any other medication (Allopathic, Ayurveda, Siddha or homeopathy), Body weight less than 45kgs and those who didn't fulfil criteria for blood donation are excluded from the study. A structured questionnaire was prepared in English and information was collected about the age of the participant, gender, blood group, total count, eosinophilic count.

History of infectious disease like typhoid, malaria, dengue, common cold, drug history, details of received blood and blood products within last one year was collected. After explaining the purpose of the study and obtaining informed written consent from the study participants and information was collected from them. Privacy was ensured through face-to-face interviews conducted by the principal interviewer using pretested structured questionnaires.

Blood is best obtained from the veins of the antecubital fossa, rubber tourniquet is applied to upper arm and the site is cleaned with 70% ethanol and allowed to dry. Selected vein was anchored by compressing the soft tissue below the puncture site with the left hand. Sterile disposable needle and syringe was used and required amount of blood is withdrawn. Blood was mixed with anticoagulant (EDTA) in the container thoroughly by gently inverting the container several times. Blood sample was sent to the lab and the sample were run in a complete blood count analyzer.

A complete blood cell (CBC) count is a blood test that provide information about the cells in voluntary blood donors. The CBC indicates the counts of RBC, WBC and platelet as well as hemoglobin, hematocrit levels. Other analyses include RBC distribution width, MCV, MCH, MCHC, WBC differential count in percentage and absolute value, platelet distribution width, platelet mean volume was obtained. Finally, the eosinophil count was categorized as mild, moderate and severe for analysis.

Data was tabulated in MS Excel and analyzed using IBM SPSS version 26.0. All the Continues variables follows normal distribution and were expressed as mean and standard deviation (SD). All quantitative data was tested for normality using Kolmogorov-Smirnov test. Comparison of more than two mean values between categories was calculated using analysis of various test as appropriate. Categorical data was presented as frequency and percentage values. Comparison of frequency data across categories was carried out using Chi square test as appropriate. For skewed data, median values and interquartile range values was computed and compared using non parametric test (Kruskal-Wallis H test). For all statistical test, a two-sided probability of $p < 0.05$ will be considered as statistically significant.

Results

Table 1 shows the number of participants in this study on eosinophilia among blood donors at a tertiary care center in Tiruchirappalli is 1,258. The mean age of the donors is 25.72 years with standard deviation 7.52 years. This indicates that most of the participants are

young adults. Females make only 0.8% whereas male donors share 99.2% as shown in gender distribution: n=1,248 males (99.2%), n=10 females (0.8%).

The distribution of blood groups among the donors was mainly O Positive accounting for 32.4% (n=407). B Positive was at 29.7% (n=374) and A Positive came third at 22.5% (n=283). Other blood groups included: O Negative, 2.6%; n=33); B Negative, 2.9%; n=36); A Negative, 2.0%; n=25); AB Positive, 7.2%; n=91) and AB Negative, 0.7%; n=9).

Median WBC counts for donors were 7.22 mm³ with an IQR of 2.89 indicating WBC counts falling within normal limits in most of the donors. The median eosinophil count was at 0.25 cells/mcL, with an IQR of 0.23, suggesting that the majority had normal levels of eosinophils.

Relative to eosinophilia, 11.3% of the donors had mild eosinophilia, while only 0.5% had moderate eosinophilia. Of these the remaining 88.2% were within the normal range of eosinophil count, meaning most donors lacked an increase in eosinophils. It is interesting to note that not a single subject manifested severe eosinophilia.

Also, none of the contributors had histories involving infectious diseases, drug use and recent blood transfusions, as all 1,258 contributors were reported to have had no such medical history. The results of the study indicate a low prevalence of eosinophilia in the donor population. Most donors fall into the normal range of eosinophil counts, while no significant comorbidities or external factors influenced the findings.

Table 1: Basic characteristics of the study participants

Basic characteristics	Number	Percentage
Mean age \pm Standard deviation in years	25.72 \pm 7.52	
Gender		
Male	1248	99.2 %
Female	10	0.8 %
Blood Group		
A Negative	25	2.0 %
A Positive	283	22.5 %
AB Negative	9	0.7 %
AB Positive	91	7.2 %
B Negative	36	2.9 %
B Positive	374	29.7 %
O Negative	33	2.6 %
O Positive	407	32.4 %
Median Total count (Inter quartile range) in mm ³	7.22 (IQR – 2.89)	
Median Eosinophil count (Inter quartile range) cells/mcL	0.25 (IQR – 0.23)	

Eosinophilia category		
Mild	142	11.3 %
Moderate	6	0.5 %
Normal	1110	88.2 %
History of Infectious disease		
Yes	0	0%
No	1258	100 %
Any drug history		
Yes	0	0%
No	1258	100 %
Received blood or blood products within one year		
Yes	0	0%
No	1258	100 %
Total	1258	100 %

Table 2 shows the average age of donors with mild eosinophilia was 26.27 ± 7.91 years and those with moderate eosinophilia was a little lower at 23.17 ± 7.93 years. The donors with normal range eosinophils had a mean age of 25.66 ± 7.47 years, but the difference in mean age among the categories was not statistically significant; $p = 0.466$).

Table 2: Comparison between Eosinophilia categories with other basic characteristics

Basic characteristics	Eosinophilia categories			p value
	Mild (n = 142)	Moderate (n = 6)	Normal (n = 1110)	
Mean age \pm Standard deviation in years	26.27 ± 7.91	23.17 ± 7.93	25.66 ± 7.47	0.466 ^{##}
Gender				
Male	139 (97.9%)	6 (100%)	1103 (99.4%)	0.169 [#]
Female	3 (2.1%)	0	7 (0.6%)	
Blood Group				
A Negative	0	0	25 (2.3%)	0.811 [#]
A Positive	30 (21.1%)	2 (33.3%)	251 (22.6%)	
AB Negative	2 (1.4%)	0	7 (0.6%)	
AB Positive	14 (9.9%)	0	77 (6.9%)	
B Negative	5 (3.5%)	0	31 (2.8%)	
B Positive	45 (31.7%)	3 (50.0%)	326 (29.4%)	
O Negative	4 (2.8%)	0	29 (2.6%)	
O Positive	42 (29.6%)	1 (16.7%)	364 (32.8%)	
Median Total count (Inter quartile range)	9.87 (IQR - 1.33)	11.41 (IQR - 1.68)	6.87 (IQR - 2.61)	* < 0.001

Gender distribution of donors in relation to the categories of eosinophilia is dominated by males in all categories. For instance, among the donors who showed slight eosinophilia, 97.9% were men. Among the donors who had moderate eosinophils, as well as donors who

showed normal eosinophils, all such donors were men at a percent rate of 99.4%. Female donors made up a very negligible percentage that is, only 2.1% in the mild group and 0.6% in the normal group. In the second category that showed moderate eosinophilia, there were no female donors. Despite these differences, the gender distribution did not reach any statistically significant difference between the two groups being compared $p = 0.169$.

The blood type grouping was also compared to determine if there exists a statistical significance association between the blood group types and the categories of eosinophilia. The comparison did not reach any statistical significance between them for $p = 0.811$, though some trends were observed. For example, the B Positive blood group appeared more frequently among those donors whose eosinophilia was moderate at 50% as compared to the others whose eosinophil counts stood at a mild level of 31.7% and normal counts of 29.4%. Similarly, the A Positive donors accounted for 33.3% of the moderate eosinophilia group, reasonably similar to the 22.6% in the normal group. Other blood groups such as O Positive, B Negative and AB Positive had blood spreads nearly evenly without extreme deviation in the categories.

The median total white blood cell count varies the most in categories of eosinophilia. The median total count of 9.87 (IQR – 1.33) mm³ for mild eosinophilia donor and an even higher median total count of 11.41 (IQR – 1.68) mm³ for moderate eosinophilia donors were greatly in contrast to the median total count of 6.87 (IQR – 2.61) mm³ in donors with normal eosinophil count. The difference of total white blood cell count between groups is statistically significant at a level of $p < 0.001$, meaning there is a relationship between the higher counts of white blood cell and the presence of eosinophilia, mainly in mild and moderate cases.

Discussion

Since eosinophilia is connected to allergy and immunologic illnesses, infectious diseases caused by parasites, and haematological disorders, its significance has been established. Blood eosinophil counts have been seen to fluctuate within an individual at different times of the day and on different days, in both healthy volunteers and those with eosinophilic illnesses. This is because a variety of variables can affect the quantity of eosinophils. However, different studies have different findings, and count variability is rarely significant enough to affect treatment.

Even though eosinophilia is a traditional analytical datum, not many investigations have determined how common it is in different diseases (25-28). The studies are therefore not comparable. The population on which most research have likely focused is that of migrants

and travellers from tropical and subtropical regions where parasitic diseases are common, with eosinophilic prevalence rates ranging from 2.3 to 28.5% (18,19). However, the majority of research has been conducted in the areas of travel medicine and tropical illnesses, which might indicate bias in these study designs (29-31). It is typically proposed that allergic disorders account for the majority of causes in western nations, whereas parasitic infections account for the majority in tropical locations in the lack of comprehensive and reliable epidemiological data (20).

This study provides demographic and haematological characteristics of blood donors with a range of eosinophilia in a tertiary care centre in Tiruchirappalli. Eosinophilia is a relatively rare finding when it comes to blood donors, but our study has elucidated various patterns and associations between eosinophilia in terms of age, gender, blood group, and white blood cell counts.

The mean age of donors in the category of mild eosinophilia is 26.27 ± 7.91 years, and the one with moderate eosinophilia of 23.17 ± 7.93 years tends to prove that the group affected due to increased levels of eosinophil counts is relatively young. The difference in the mean age among these categories is not statistically significant ($p = 0.466$). This finding was consistent with others where there was not a statistically significant impact of age on eosinophilia in healthy donors, thus indicating that, for healthy blood donors, age might not be a determinant factor of a person's level of eosinophils. The slightly lower mean age in the moderate eosinophilia group may indicate younger donors are a little more prone to higher counts of eosinophils due to undiagnosed allergic conditions, parasitic diseases, or other subclinical conditions. It needs to be evaluated further in larger studies in terms of establishing any definitive pattern.

A striking predominance of male donors was found in all groups of eosinophilia, while the percentage of female donors was low in the mild and normal group of eosinophilia, and there was no female donor in the group of moderate eosinophilia. Interestingly, these differences did not reach statistical significance regarding gender distribution between categories of eosinophilia ($p = 0.169$). This male predominance may also be due to general gender prevalence of blood donors, which in most regions, including India, skews heavily in favour of males. Previous studies have suggested that in fact, there is not a gender bias in eosinophilia and hormonal differences play only a minor role in modifying immune responses. However, the low number of female donors makes it difficult to draw firm conclusions about gender-related differences in eosinophils levels among the donors.

Though no statistically significant association was observed between blood group and eosinophilia ($p = 0.811$), some trends have been noted. The moderate prevalence of B Positive and A Positive among donors with eosinophilia, might be suggesting a potential but not conclusive relationship between the blood groups with levels of eosinophils. While still showing a considerable deviation in the moderate eosinophilia group, it has to be said that B Positive donors show a marked deviation with 50%, equalled only by the frequency of A Positive donors, and all of these trends need further study with a larger sample size to ascertain whether blood group plays any meaningful role in the occurrence of eosinophilia.

The most interesting finding of this study is the fact that the total WBC count is really well associated with eosinophilia since the value of $p < 0.001$. Those donors who had mild and moderate eosinophilia presented notably higher median WBC counts: (9.87 mm^3 and 11.41 mm^3) respectively as opposed to normal donors with the eosinophil count at 6.87 mm^3 . This discovering reconfirms the very well-established role of eosinophils as an element of body's immune response, with raised eosinophil counts usually being found with rising WBC count. In the context of current study, significant difference in total WBC count between groupings by the criterion of eosinophilia indicates the tendency for the higher the WBC count, the more likely it is that eosinophilia is concurrently present, particularly in cases of mild to moderate eosinophilia. This finding is in line with literature associating high WBC counts with a wide range of conditions, such as allergic diseases, parasitic infections, and certain haematological disorders often associated with eosinophilia.

In the search for causes and therapeutic interventions, the degree of eosinophilia was substantially correlated with diagnoses, laboratory tests, and consultations with internists. These procedures adhere to the most recent recommendations for clinical practice (1,11). We recommend that all medical professionals be aware of the need of determining the precise cause of eosinophilia and require a diagnostic work-up in accordance with this necessity, particularly in cases where the illness is moderate to severe. The possibility that a high AEC level is connected to haematologic cancers has been repeatedly reported (32,33).

Moreover, compared to patients visiting general practitioner clinics, premium checkup clinics offered a much better chance of screening for probable causes and therapies for eosinophilia patients. We surmise that because family medicine professionals at premium checkup clinics tend to have greater experience than interns in general practitioner clinics, they are better suited to identify and diagnose eosinophilia.

This is one of the few studies in the literature that we are aware of that examines the prevalence of eosinophilia seen during routine health exams and the following medical

therapy that occurs. Furthermore, the duration of the follow-up period to ascertain the eosinophilia patients' outcomes in this study was adequate to provide a logical conclusion regarding the nature and scope of the issue as well as potential treatments. Our study was not without limits, though. First, some information was lost due to the retrospective research design, including the doctor's management (medical history, physical examination, laboratory testing, and anthelmintic medication therapy). We presume that when doctors diagnosed eosinophilia, they meant to determine what caused it.

For instance, if we saw that a doctor diagnosed eosinophilia, we would infer that the doctor checked for lymphadenopathy or hepatosplenomegaly as potential causes of the condition. Nonetheless, some doctors do standard tests for lymphadenopathy or hepatosplenomegaly at routine physicals, even if they are not looking for the reason of eosinophilia. Second, it was impossible for us to say with certainty if "spontaneous recovery" meant a complete and spontaneous recovery from eosinophilia or whether other medical professionals' specialised care—like over-the-counter anthelmintic medication—was obtained. Third, inadequate data from a single visit prevented us from evaluating the outcome in one-third of our patients.

Recommendations

We recommend that healthcare providers be aware of the significance and high frequency of eosinophilia as it may be a sign of more serious conditions like malignancies. Therefore, after eosinophilia has been diagnosed, a thorough medical history and physical examination should be undertaken for each patient. Based on potential causes whose participation is suspected, further laboratory testing may be carried out. In addition to stool examinations, serology testing for common tissue-invasive parasites should be undertaken in endemic locations where parasite infections are widespread. Another approach in poor nations is empirical anthelmintic medication therapy, the specifics of which are determined by epidemiological research conducted in each region. Additionally crucial to the treatment of patients with eosinophilia is follow-up CBC.

Until a resolution is reached or the source of eosinophilia is found, follow-up CBC tests have to be carried out. In order to rule out potentially dangerous underlying causes, such as malignancy, invasive testing should be taken into consideration for individuals exhibiting chronic eosinophilia. Furthermore, efforts should be made to raise physician awareness and understanding about eosinophilia, especially among recently graduated physicians. The best course of treatment for eosinophilia patients may be determined in the future by prospective

cohort studies. For example, a follow-up CBC following anthelmintic medication therapy may be necessary to confirm the existence of parasite infections. New insights into the diagnosis and management of eosinophilia might come from multi-centre research in the future.

Limitations

We were unable to access the medical history that would have allowed us to confirm the findings or identify the potential diseases involved, and the study patients are most likely not a representative sample of the general population. These are the main limitations and biases of this study. Additionally, the retrospective design of the study and the single blood sample are both causes of bias. These factors mean that before extrapolating the results to the whole population, care should be taken in how you interpret the data.

Conclusion

A common abnormal condition that is often found during routine physical examinations is eosinophilia. The majority of general practitioners, particularly in patients with low severity, are not well-versed in the diagnosis or underlying aetiology of the condition. In endemic locations where parasite infections are common, empirical anthelmintic treatment produced good outcomes for the management of eosinophilia. To find the underlying reason, further research is necessary in individuals with chronic eosinophilia, particularly in those who have malignancy.

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